

Influence of seedling rate on tungro (RTV) incidence at Cuttack

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A trial under protected and unprotected conditions measured influence of number of seedlings per hill on RTV incidence. Protection was 0.01% decamethrin sprayed weekly up to heading. TN1 (susceptible) and Ratna (tolerant) were planted in 3- × 3-m plots in a randomized block design with 3 replications.

Ten days after transplanting (DT), infected Jaya tillers were transplanted around each plot to inoculate unprotected plots. Protected plots were not inoculated. Disease incidence was recorded 60 DT.

Disease incidence in TN1 was 100% in all unprotected plots; it varied in

Effect of number of seedlings per hill on RTV incidence and grain yield in rice cultivars TN1 and Ratna.^a Orissa, India.

Seedlings/hill (no.)	Disease incidence (%) in unprotected plots		Grain yield (t/ha)			
			Unprotected		Protected	
	TN1	Ratna	TN1	Ratna	TN1	Ratna
1	100	62 d	0.5 a	1.8 c	1.5 b	2.8 b
2	100	42 c	0.5 a	2.3 bc	2.1 a	3.4 ab
3	100	28 b	0.5 a	2.5 b	2.1 a	3.4 ab
4	100	12 a	0.5 a	3.1 a	2.0 a	3.6 ab
6	100	13 a	0.6 a	3.1 a	2.2 a	3.6 ab
8	100	9 a	0.6 a	3.1 a	2.0 a	3.8 a

^aIn each column, values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at P = 0.05 by DMRT.

tolerant cultivar Ratna (see table). Disease incidence gradually decreased with seedling rate.

Grain yield differed between protected and unprotected plots. Yields of TN1 were higher under protected conditions. Under protected conditions, yields did not significantly differ at 2 to 5 seedlings/hill, but were lower for 1 seedling/hill. Yields of

Ratna under unprotected conditions gradually increased with numbers of seedlings/hill; there was no significant yield difference among 4, 6, and 8 seedlings/hill.

Number of seedlings per hill had no effect on susceptible TN1, especially under unprotected conditions. Four seedlings per hill is optimum for Ratna. □

Growth and virulence of two isolates of *Sarocladium oryzae* causing sheath rot (ShR) in rice

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ShR is caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* and *S. attenuatum*, the former being more prevalent. To obtain information on the variation in growth and virulence of *S. oryzae*, two isolates that differed in colony color were used. The mycelium of isolate 283-P was slightly pinkish, isolate 1183-W appeared whitish on potato dextrose agar medium. Three areas were studied: morphology of the conidia and conidiophores, growth of the two isolates in three semisolid and liquid media, and virulence of the isolates in different rice genotypes.

No difference in morphology was found. Growth in Czapek's solution agar (CZA), malt yeast extract agar (MYA), and potato dextrose agar (PDA) were similar, but isolate

Linear growth of 2 isolates of *Sarocladium oryzae* in 3 media at 28 ± 2 °C.

1183-W grew better than isolate 283-P in both semisolid and liquid media (see figure).

Thirty-seven varieties and lines at early booting were inoculated in the field with infected rice grain culture of the two isolates. The infected grain was pressed, with slight wounding, onto the sheath tissue of the flag leaf of a tiller and attached with scotch tape. Disease severity or lesion length was measured at hard-dough to maturity.

Disease severity in genotypes differed. A significant isolate × variety interaction indicates the possibility that the isolates are distinct strains or races. Except for Kalarharsall, the difference in disease severity was not great. The mean disease severity of the 37 entries was significantly higher for isolate 283-P (13.1 cm) than for isolate 1183-W (11.4 cm), suggesting that 283-P is more virulent (see table). For these isolates, there was no relation between growth in culture media and virulence.

The mean disease severity based on lesion length shows that only one genotype, BR51-46-5-C1, may be considered moderately resistant (lesion length less than 6.5 cm); all others were moderately to highly susceptible (lesion length more than 6.5 cm). □

Reactions of 37 varieties and lines to 2 isolates of *Sarocladium oryzae* causing sheath rot of rice.

Variety or line	Mean length of lesion ^a (cm)	
	Isolate 283-P	Isolate 1183-W
B2489B-PN-1-76-8	24.0	21.6
BR51-46-5-C1	6.3	3.0
BR51-49-6-HR50	14.4	5.3
BR425-48-1-4-1-2-1	9.7	3.3
BR425-53-2-1-1-4-3	11.0	6.6
BR425-87-1-1-2-3-1	11.5	11.5
BR425-93-3-1-2-3-4	9.3	15.0
BR425-110-2-1-1-2-3	18.5	14.0
BR425-110-2-1-1-6-1	11.3	6.0
BR425-177-1-3-1-4-4	10.3	9.8
BR425-177-1-3-1-5-3	16.9	10.6
BR1242-6-1-1	15.0	9.2
BR1356-10-1-6	9.0	6.2
BR1356-13-2-1	19.8	13.0
BR1356-40-3-1	14.7	2.5
BR1356-40-4-4	8.7	7.5
BR1412-5-1-1	10.1	20.6
IR54	8.2	15.8
IR34	10.3	9.3
IR10781-75-3-2	18.3	15.4
IR17983-45-3-2-3-1	7.2	12.3
IR18047-3-2-1-3	9.5	11.8
IR25166-14-1-1	18.5	7.3
IR25173-2-5-2	12.8	10.4
IR25173-5-1-2	16.0	9.3
IR25177-3-1-2	16.0	9.0
Kachamota	10.0	14.2
Kalarharsall	4.3	18.0
KAU 2084	13.2	19.3
M12C-34-3	9.0	7.6
M61B-1-1-2	15.3	13.5
M61B-11-2-1	15.0	6.6
M61B-18-2-1	9.0	9.3
M66B-30-1	14.8	13.5
Ptb-18	17.5	10.2
RNR74229	19.8	21.5
RP1125-104-2-1-1	20.5	19.8
Mean	13.1	11.4

^aMeans of 3 replications. LSD for comparing means: (a) Isolates within a variety = 15.9 at P .05, (b) Varieties within an isolate = 5.9 at P .05, (c) Isolates among all varieties = 1.0 at P .05.

Studies on ratoon performance of leaf blast-susceptible varieties at ARS, Ponnampet, Karnataka

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In the National Screening Nursery (NSN) of 1985-86 kharif, 50 rice cultures were screened for reaction to leaf blast (Bl). None of the cultures were resistant to leaf or neck Bl; ratings varied from 7 to 9 cm on a 0-9 scale, with practically no yield.

The culms of the diseased entries were cut 10-15 cm from the base of the

Performance of main crop and ratoon crop of promising cultures in Mandya, India.

Variety	Main crop				Ratoon crop ^a			
	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Bl rating		Yield (t/ha)	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Yield (t/ha)
			Leaf Bl	Neck Bl (%)				
IET9667	86	133	2	90	0	36	99	1.7
IET9668	89	125	0	100	0	38	96	1.7
IET9670	94	114	1	90	0.1	41	91	1.6
Intan (check)	115	87	7	90	0	Ratoon crop destroyed by leaf Bl		

^aThe test varieties had neither leaf nor neck Bl.

plant and allowed to ratoon. Only 3 of the 50 cultures gave rise to productive tillers. These cultures were free from Bl and yielded an average 1.6 t/ha. In the

ratoon, plant height was reduced 46.6% and days to flowering 42.6% (see table). □